

Unveiling Elementary Teachers' Experiences In Implementing Blended Learning

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Abstract. This study unveiled the blended learning implementation of elementary teachers. A total of 10 public elementary school teachers from Bangoy District, Division of Davao City participated in this research. Employing a phenomenological approach to extract the ideas of the participants. An in-depth interview was employed to gain insights with regard to their respective lived experiences, coping mechanisms and insights and lessons learned in implementing blended learning. Through thematic analysis, key themes emerged: challenges in technology access, increased teacher workload, and learner engagement setbacks. To overcome challenges in blended learning implementation, three themes were identified: maximizing available resources, teacher collaboration and training, and parental and community involvement. The insights and lessons drawn from the findings of the study were emphasizing flexibility in teaching, employing digital literacy, and strengthening teacher and learner collaboration. Findings emphasized that a well-structured blended learning framework can optimize educational outcomes, making learning more engaging and accessible. Moreover, the study emphasizes the necessity of institutional support, parental and community assistance and innovative pedagogical strategies to ensure the sustainability and effectiveness of blended learning. The insights gained reinforce the importance of blended learning as a transformative tool in modern education.

KEY WORDS

1. Blended learning modality 2. flexible learning 3. digital pedagogy

Date Received: April 05, 2025 — Date Reviewed: May 15, 2025 — Date Published: June 18, 2025

1. Introduction

Blended learning modality combines traditional face-to-face instruction with synchronous and asynchronous online educational resources and modular activities, creating a dynamic and flexible learning environment that enhances learner engagement and accommodates diverse learning styles. Delving deeper to it is essential because it offers a flexible and innovative approach to education that can enhance active participation and involvement of learners, address diverse learning needs, and prepare educators and learners for increasingly digital world. Globally, many teachers were having a hard time adapting their instructional strategies to cater to diverse learning needs and preferences in a blended learning environment, while balancing the demands of in-person and online teaching can be overwhelming, requiring teachers to redesign lesson plans, manage learners' interactions across different platforms, and continuously assess the effectiveness of their teaching methods (Gilmour, 2020). In Vietnam, imple-

menting blended learning modality presents several challenges for teachers. Many teachers may not be familiar with the technology required for effective online instruction and may need additional support to develop the necessary skills. This can include learning how to use learning management systems, creating engaging digital content, and managing virtual classrooms effectively (Kareem, 2019). While in California, in some schools, teachers are still facing difficulties in utilizing technology and having a hard time implementing the blended learning approach. While the reported effects of blended learning are mixed, few have explored deeper into the possible challenges surrounding the integration of blended learning, especially with the experiences of primary school teachers (Tucker et al., 2018). In Texas, another significant challenge is ensuring equitable access to technology for all learners. Teachers often face the difficulty of addressing the digital divide, where some learners may not have access to reliable internet connections or the necessary devices for participating in online learning. This can lead to disparities in learner engagement and achievement (Gurley, 2018). In the Philippines, the Department of Education offers different learning delivery modalities that the region, division, or school may adopt depending on the geographical location, socio-economic status, and quality of learner. Educators find themselves at the crossroads of implementing blended learning modality through innovation and tradition, grappling with questions of pedagogical efficacy and equitable access to technology. The socio-emotional aspects of elementary education pose additional challenges in a digital environment, with the varying levels of technological proficiency among teachers and learners which add a layer of complexity to the implementation of blended learning (Moran, 2020). Cannot be denied that teaching blended learning modality has weaknesses and threats. Teachers are having a hard time in implementing the lessons without a face-to-face teaching, as well as having uncertainty if parents really follow the process in guiding and teaching their own sons and daughters at home. These are the predicaments that teachers were having during the implementation of blended learning through the use of modular learning materials and virtual classes either through synchronous or asynchronous approach (Alvarez, 2020). This qualitative study is to unveil how teachers perceive the implementation of blended learning modality, its challenges and how they cope with the problems encountered alongside with its execution. As part of this research purpose, the researcher will explore elementary teachers' lived experiences in the implementation of blended learning modality, the issues/challenges they have encountered, and discover how they cope with the execution of blended learning modality during this new normal class setting.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this phenomenological study is to unveil the relevance of the lived experiences of teachers in the implementation of blended learning, with the experiences of teachers in the implementation of blended learning system, supplemented with the type of blended learning, and accompanied by the issues and challenges of blended learning system could bring out the lead experiences of the elementary school teachers. In the present time, education is the key to economic survival. The part of blended learning system in the new normal class setting is increasing in occurrence and importance as educators understand its value and adjust to its impact. Consequently, blended learning in teaching is the tool that will help teachers and students, with the guidance of the school principal, to create new partnerships and unleash deeper learning. In addition, authentic learning through the use of blended learning system, allow learners to develop competencies, master content knowledge, and apply learning outcomes to

contexts beyond the classroom. Therefore, blended learning system in teaching is a tool and resource working ubiquitously with the construction of knowledge and development of the new normal educational scheme. Specifically, the study aimed to draw significant information from the participants in terms of the lived experiences in their insights in the implementation of blended learning approach as drawn from the findings of the study that will be conducted in Bangoy District, Davao City Division. This study will be beneficial to the Department of Education, school principals, teachers, and students.

1.2. *Research Questions*—This study was conducted to unveil the lived experiences of elementary school teachers in the implementation of blended learning modality. The direction of this study was set by the following specific research questions:

- (1) What are the lived experiences of teachers in implementing blended learning modality?
- (2) What are the coping mechanism of the problem encountered implementing the blended learning modality?
- (3) What are the insights or lessons learned from the experiences implementing blended learning modality?

1.3. *Definition of Terms*—Department of Education The results may be applied by the Department of Education in assisting the school principals to address some issues in relation to the implementation of blended learning modality in the new normal class setting. School Principals Through this study, the school principals can make data-driven decisions based on insights gained from the study, ensuring effective resource allocation and strategic planning for the implementation of blended learning. Also, it may equip school principals with the knowledge and insights necessary to foster a conducive environment for effective, efficient, and equitable education in the digital age. Teachers Teach-

ers will also benefit from this study, since they can gain insights into effective blended learning strategies, enabling them to diversify their teaching methods and cater to different learning styles within the classroom. It can also empower teachers with the knowledge and tools to create dynamic, student-centered classrooms that leverage the advantages of both traditional and digital learning environments.

Students As for students, the benefits of blended learning for elementary learners incorporate personalized learning, increased engagement, digital literacy development, and cultivation of skills that crucial for success in the 21st century.

1.4. *Theoretical Lens*—This study is supported by the Social Learning Theory of Bandura (1977) which is based on the idea that we learn from our interactions with others in a social context. Thus, the experiences of teachers in the implementation of blended learning system will be influential to the teaching-learning process of the elementary school teachers. Eventually, through the implementation of blended learning system, teachers will be able to integrate, especially if their observational experi-

ences are positive ones, the blended learning system in their teaching-learning process. Principles of social learning are assumed to operate in same way throughout life. Insofar as exposure to new influential, powerful models like the blended learning system, who control resources and may occur at life stage, new learning just like the implementation of blended learning system in teaching, is always possible. People learn from one another through observation; imitation; and modeling. Based on these gen-

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

eral principles, learning can occur without a change in behavior. In other words, learning has to be represented by a permanent change in behavior; thus, blended learning system in teaching can be learned through observation. It includes the development of the lead experiences of teachers that could lead to the full implementation of blended learning system. It is also focused on how children and adults operate cognitively on their social experiences and how these cognitions then influence behavior and development. Another theory that gives strength to the study is the Constructivist Learning Theory by Jerome Bruner (1973), which emphasized that less learning as the product of passive transmission than a process of active construction whereby the learners construct their own knowledge based upon prior knowledge. CLT theorized that learning requires learners to demonstrate their skills by constructing their own knowledge when solving real-world problems. The constructivist model calls for

learner-centered instruction because learners are assumed to learn better when they are forced to explore and discover things by themselves. Technology should be employed in ways that teaching strategies that are learner-centered develop in classrooms. Without a doubt, teachers are responsible for the ICT development in the field of education. In the technological revolution and the information age, using technology in teaching becomes a fact of life. Likewise, dialogue simulations and role play exercises should be increasingly used by the teacher to promote communication skills. ICT tools should not only be used for every listening and speaking activity, but most importantly during the planning and design stage of a lesson the teacher should give due consideration of when, when not and how to integrate. These provided safe spaces to negotiate understandings and for teachers to scaffold and support each other in shifting to blended learning.

2. Methodology

This chapter of the study presented the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. Exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitated the design and implementation, which were elaborated in this chapter. The three most common qualitative methods were participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus group discussions. Each method was particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation was appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behavior in its usual context. In-depth interviews (IDI) were optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics were explored. Focus groups were effective in eliciting data on the cultural norms of a group and in generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Phenomenology is one of the fundamental traditions of qualitative inquiry that investigates human lived experiences. It describes individual encounters with a phenomenon in universal terms or context. The description of the phenomenon described what the individuals saw and how they saw it (Creswell, 2020). Also, Phenomenology has applications in various fields, including psychology, sociology, and education, offering a rich and nuanced understanding of the intricate tapestry of human consciousness. Through in-depth interviews, observations, and analysis of lived experiences, phenomenology contributes to unraveling the complexities of human existence and shedding light on the subjective dimensions of our shared reality.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It established the background used for drawing conclusions and making decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions had different types and were elaborated below. Good research involved the selection of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stange (1987) traces 'paradigm' back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm) meaning pattern, model or example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm was an action of submitting to a view. This view was supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000) who defended a research paradigm a "basic set of belief that guide action", dealing with first principles, "ultimates" or the researcher's worldview or philosophy. *Ontology* This part of the research pertained to how the issue related to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2020), reality was subjective and multiple, as perceived by participants in the study. The ontological issue addressed the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. Reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities existed, such as those of the researcher, the individuals being investigated, and the readers or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the experiences of teachers in implementing the blended learning modality were discussed by the participants, and their strategies for addressing challenges and educational insights were examined. In this study, the researcher relied on voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes, themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct for the commonality and discreteness of responses. It was made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the

result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progresses. Epistemology This referred to the awareness of how knowledge claims were justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Creswell (2020) stated that, based on the epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between himself or herself and the participants. He suggested that, as a researcher, he or she collaborated, spent time in the field with participants, and became an "insider." Based on Davidson (2000), the researcher identified phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best approach for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers "held explicit beliefs." The intention of this study was to gather information from the participants or teachers in public elementary schools in Bangoy District, Davao City Division regarding their lived experiences during the implementation of blended learning. Axiol-

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Methodology was different from method. Methodology was creative and responsive approach to understand questions and subject matter while method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study the dilemma in the blended learning implementation experienced by the public elementary school teachers in Bangoy District, Davao City Division were gathered through an In-Depth Interview (IDI) as well as through Focus Group Discussion (FGD) were extracted from the participants. The researcher's effort in knowing the deeper meaning of the blended learning implementation of public elementary school teachers became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means of which Gerodias, (2013) considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences and

ogy It referred to the role of values in research. Creswell (2020) asserted that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggested that the researcher openly discussed the values that shaped the narrative and incorporated their interpretation alongside the interpretation of the participants. The researcher ensured the dignity and significance of every detail of information obtained from the participants. Recognizing the personal and value-laden nature of the data gathered, the researcher carefully preserved the integrity of the participants' responses and interpreted them in alignment with their perspectives. Rhetoric It meant reporting reality through the eyes of the research participants. This was important because it ensured that the research objectively presented what was observed and heard from the participants. The research utilized a personal voice, qualitative terms, and limited definitions. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person to elucidate the experiences of teachers as they implemented the blended learning system.

phenomena". By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by unveiling the experience of elementary school teachers in implementing blended learning in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols and meaning of the experiences presented. Phenomenological research was based on two premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Morrissey Higgs (2006) that experience was a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge, and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into

the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology which concerns with that “what” and the “how” (Moustakas, 1994), the researcher projected that the blended learn-

2.3. Design and Procedure—This research employed the phenomenological approach to illuminate specific phenomena by identifying them through the way they were perceived in a given situation. In the human sphere, this typically involved gathering in-depth information and perceptions through inductive, qualitative methods such as interviews, discussions, and participant observation, and presenting them from the perspective of the research participants. Phenomenology focused on studying experiences from the individual’s perspective, setting aside preconceived assumptions and habitual ways of perceiving. The purpose of the phe-

2.4. Research Participants—Qualitative analyses typically required a smaller sample size compared to quantitative analyses. The sample size needed to be large enough to capture feedback on most or all perceptions. Reaching most or all perceptions ensured the attainment of saturation, which occurred when adding more participants no longer provided new perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (1967) recommended the concept of saturation for determining an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (2020) suggested a range of five to 25 participants. There were no strict rules for determining the ideal sample size in qualitative research, as it was best determined by the time available, the resources at hand, and the study objectives (Patton, 1990). Purposive sampling was employed to identify participants for this study. This non-probability sampling method was selected based on the characteristics of the population and the study’s objectives. Purpo-

ing implementation as experienced by the elementary school teachers were explored and insights drawn the basis for the possible future researches and policy analysis in relation to this research.

phenomenological approach was to highlight specific phenomena by examining how they were perceived by individuals in a particular context. In this study, the researcher collected rich information and insights using qualitative methods such as interviews, discussions, and participant observation. These data were analyzed and presented from the viewpoint of the research participants (Stanage, 1987). Phenomenology proved to be a relevant philosophical methodology, enabling the researcher to uncover and interpret the experiences of public elementary school teachers in the implementation of the blended learning system.

sive sampling, also referred to as selective or subjective sampling, allowed for the deliberate selection of participants who met specific criteria. The researcher chose ten elementary school teachers for the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. A total of ten public elementary school teachers from Bangoy District, Davao City Division were invited to participate. The inclusion criteria required that participants be currently teaching in a public school within Bangoy District, Davao City Division, and have at least three years of teaching experience in public elementary schools. The results obtained were used to identify emerging themes and patterns based on their lived experiences. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design, as participants were selected according to the study’s specific criteria (Creswell, 2020). This method, also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, ensured that participants were purposefully chosen to enhance the authenticity of the findings (Marshall, 1996).

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Ethical considerations were essential in the design of this research study. The researcher carefully addressed various ethical issues concerning the participants during the fieldwork. These considerations were regarded as one of the most critical aspects of the research. The researcher adhered to ethical principles to uphold the integrity of the study, ensuring the dissemination of authentic knowledge, truth, and the prevention of errors. Social Value Research played a crucial role in society. In this study, social value was centered on the experiences of teachers. It was specifically conducted among elementary school teachers to gain insights into their challenges. Furthermore, the study served as a foundation for higher authorities to develop programs and resolutions that would benefit elementary classroom teachers. The social issue that motivated the researcher was the challenges faced by elementary school teachers in implementing the blended learning system. Informed Consent In conducting this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2013), was upheld. Participants were invited with the assurance that their involvement in the research was entirely voluntary and based on a clear understanding of sufficient information. The process of participant recruitment and selection was documented in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was essential for conducting an informed and ethical academic inquiry, particularly in phenomenological research (Pierre, 2012). All participants had received an informed consent form before their interviews were scheduled and before they took part in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed acknowledgment, granting consent and indicating their willingness to participate in the study. The informed consent letter served to introduce the research, provide contact information, explain the study's purpose, request voluntary partici-

pation, and outline the type of information expected from the participants. All participants were required to sign and return the letter of consent to the researcher before engaging in the study.

Vulnerability of Research Participants The participants in this study were fully capable of responding to the research instrument, as they were all professional teachers in public elementary schools. The researcher ensured that they had access to clear communication and support throughout the study. Contact information was provided so participants could easily reach the researcher for any clarifications or questions regarding the research. **Risks, Benefits and Safety** The recruitment of respondents was conducted without coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Additionally, respondents were provided with the contact information of the panel chair or panel members in case they had any questions related to the study. If respondents experienced any discomfort or inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelled to participate in any way. The researcher ensured the safety and well-being of respondents throughout the interview process. The in-depth interviews were conducted in a secure location and scheduled at a time convenient for the participants. A primary concern of this study was upholding the Treaty Principle of Protection, which emphasized respect for privacy, confidentiality, and minimizing risks. To safeguard participant anonymity, pseudonyms were assigned to each informant, preventing the disclosure of their identities. Any potential risks were further minimized by implementing all necessary measures to ensure participant confidentiality. **Privacy and Confidentiality of Information** This study adhered to the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data could not be traced back to its original sources, thereby protecting the identities of the participants. Utmost care was taken to maintain the anonymity of data sources, and any printed output generated

from this study was kept confidential. Furthermore, all relevant issues were carefully considered to prevent any conflicts of interest between the researcher and the respondents. Any form of misleading information or biased representation of primary data findings was strictly avoided to uphold the integrity of the research. Justice The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they needed to respond with complete honesty when answering the interview questions and that any communication related to the research should also be conducted with integrity. Additionally, they were informed that they would be the first to benefit from the results of the study. Transparency The results of the study were made accessible to the respondents and the heads of the participating schools, as the information was available and stored on CDs or other storage devices, which could be requested from the researcher. Additionally, by reviewing the study's findings, junior high school teachers became more aware of its significance and its contribution to their well-being. Furthermore, each participant was informed of their right to withdraw their information at any time before the completion of the data collection process. They were also given the opportunity to review and verify their individual transcripts after the interviews had been conducted. This allowed participants to amend or remove any information they felt might identify them. The researcher retained the right to use pseudonyms and modify names or non-significant dates to protect the participants' identities in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher The researcher ensured that she possessed the necessary qualifications to conduct the study. She had completed the academic requirements and

passed the comprehensive examination prior to thesis writing, which was the final requirement for obtaining the master's degree. Additionally, the researcher was qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. Furthermore, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study reached its completion. Adequacy of Facilities The researcher ensured that the study could be completed successfully within the specified time-frame and that she was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee contributed to the enhancement of the paper by providing valuable suggestions and recommendations for its improvement. Additionally, the researcher ensured that she had sufficient funds to sustain and complete the research. Thus, the study was expected to be completed within the targeted time-frame. Community Involvement The researcher showed respect to the local tradition, culture and views of the respondents in this study. Moreover, this study did not involve any use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, and specifically, in the recruitment of the participants, or methods of data collection. Furthermore, the researcher necessarily expressed great pleasure for the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the Researcher The researcher respected other works by properly citing the author and rewrite what someone else has said his or her own way. The researcher also used quotes to indicate that the text has been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assured that honesty was present in working the manuscript and no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data or results is included, or purposefully put forward conclusions that are not accurate.

2.6. *Role of the Researcher*—The researcher had the responsibility to uncover, trans-

fer, and apply knowledge for the benefit of educational institutions. To fulfill this duty, the re-

researcher undertook the following roles throughout the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research The researcher conducted interviews with the participants and guided them through the process. Ideas and responses were interpreted based on existing literature and related studies rather than personal knowledge, thoughts, or feelings to prevent bias. Expert in Qualitative Methods The researcher correctly implemented the qualitative research method. To achieve this, she assessed her own capabilities and sought guidance from the research adviser and other research professionals. This support helped her demonstrate competence in explaining the study without influencing participants, conducting interviews in accordance with the research design, making appropriate field observations, selecting relevant artifacts, images, and journal entries, and employing Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis accurately. Collector and Keeper of Data The researcher ensured that various methods were used to document what was said and done during interviews and focus group discussions, such as taking handwritten notes or using audio and/or video recordings. These recordings were transcribed verbatim before data analysis

2.7. *Data Collection*—The following are the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Securing Endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School The researcher asked an endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School of The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc. as one of the documents needed for submission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent in asking permission to conduct study. Asking Permission from the Schools Division Superintendent The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified schools. The researcher will send a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with the attached Chapter

began. All records were securely stored, as they contained sensitive information crucial to the research. Throughout the data collection process, the researcher prioritized safeguarding participants and their data. Clear mechanisms for data protection were communicated to participants and were approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the study commenced.

Analyst of Data The researcher analyzed the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspectives by interpreting data, transcribing and verifying responses, identifying underlying meanings, coding, and theming. She ensured that the findings accurately represented the participants' experiences and that their voices were authentically reflected in the study. Organizer and Presenter of Data The researcher systematically presented the research problem along with related literature and studies that supported it. The findings of the study were organized and presented according to the research questions, with themes illustrating how each question was addressed. Additionally, the researcher provided recommendations for future directions and discussed the study's implications for the improvement of educational policies and practices.

1 and 2 together with the research instrument which explains the objectives of the study and the identification of the participants. The researcher will wait for the response of the SDS before the conduct of it. Asking Permission from the Public Schools District Supervisor and the School Heads After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the public school's district supervisor and the principals of the schools explaining about the study to be conducted in their school. Obtaining Consent from the Participants The researcher asked permission from the participants. They were formally oriented about the study and of the process they shall go through as participants. Conducting the

Interview The researcher conducted the in-depth interview using the interview guide questions. The profile of the participants was taken, jotted down notes, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listens and responded actively during the interviews.

Transcribing the Responses of the Interviewees The researcher transcribed the responses of the interviewees precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. If the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it to English language. Data

Coding and Thematic Content Analysis After the transcription, the data will then be categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted and individual data within the participants was compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needs further explanation and input from the participants. Additional information gathered were examined thoroughly and integrate it into the existing body of data. After which, data were compared and contrasted between the participants in order to come up with patterns and trends.

2.8. Data Analysis—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews with the use of Creswell’s Model specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2020) themes in qualitative research are similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data was common to all forms of qualitative analysis, the researcher immersed herself in, and became intimately familiar with, their data; reading and re-reading the data and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding Was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis, involves generating pithy labels for important features of the data of relevance to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding was not simply a method of data reduction; it was also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data item and ends this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts.

Searching for themes Was coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to

each theme. **Reviewing themes** The researcher reflected on whether the themes presented a convincing and compelling story about the data and proceeded to define nature of each individual theme and their relationships. To achieve, Thematic Content Analysis was employed. This method provided a descriptive presentation of qualitative data, where each theme was analyzed in detail by identifying its ‘essence’ and constructing a concise, impactful, and informative name (Andersen, 2013). In addition, to enhance validity and create a more in-depth understanding of the phenomenon, the researcher employed Environmental Triangulation. This technique analyzed the results of the study using different methods of data collection. The key aspect was identifying which environmental factors, if any, influenced the information received during the study. These environmental factors were altered to determine whether the findings remained consistent across different settings (David, 2005). This form of triangulation involved varying settings, locations, and external conditions such as time, day, or season in which the study took place. The goal was to assess whether these factors influenced the collected information. If the findings remained consistent despite these variations, validity was established. **Writing Up** The process of writing-

up involved weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to present a coherent and

persuasive account of the findings while contextualizing them in relation to existing literature.

2.9. Framework of Analysis—The framework analysis of this research was designed to be flexible, allowing the researcher to either collect all the data first and then analyze it or conduct data analysis simultaneously during the data collection process. During the analysis stage, the gathered data was sifted, charted, and sorted according to key issues and themes. This study employed a qualitative research method, ensuring that rigorous and systematic steps were observed in analyzing the information collected from the teacher-participants. The data analysis followed the steps outlined by O'Connor and Gibson (2003) for qualitative data analysis. *Organizing the Data* The data was arranged systematically to facilitate easy examination, enabling the researcher to go through each topic efficiently to identify relevant concepts and themes. *Finding and Organizing Ideas and Concepts* Recurrent words or ideas were identified and categorized into codes or thematic groups, ensuring a structured approach to data analy-

sis. *Building Over-Archiving Themes in the Data* Each response category contained one or more themes that provided a deeper understanding of the data. Different categories were merged under a primary overarching theme to ensure coherence. *Ensuring Reliability and Validity in the Data Analysis and in the Findings* The credibility of the findings was reinforced by confirming them through multiple independent sources. Their validity was further enhanced when corroborated by different instruments measuring the same phenomenon. In addition to these steps, the researcher also engaged in two additional processes. *Writing* The output of the data analysis was drafted by weaving together the narratives and relevant literature, creating a coherent and meaningful interpretation of the findings. *Presentation* The results were presented comprehensively through thematic and artistic representations, including graphs and illustrations, to effectively communicate the study's insights.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The trustworthiness of the study was established through credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. In qualitative research, ensuring trustworthiness was crucial, as the results and findings relied heavily on the process undertaken by the researcher. The reliability of a research study was essential in determining its value. Given the nature of qualitative research, honesty in handling data and reporting details was a fundamental requirement. Trustworthiness ensured that the researcher's work was valuable, shareable, and something to take pride in. *Credibility* Referred to the researcher's confidence in the truthfulness of the study's findings. The researcher-maintained integrity

throughout the study, believing that honesty in all aspects was essential for meaningful success. With no derogatory records or administrative issues that could compromise integrity, the researcher upheld credibility. Lincoln and Guba (2000) emphasized that credibility pertained to internal consistency, stressing the importance of ensuring rigor in the research process and effectively communicating this rigor to others. *Transferability* Was demonstrated by showing that the study's findings could be applicable to other contexts, including similar situations, populations, or phenomena. The researcher had previously explored the effects of blended learning, recognizing its significance in the modern educational landscape. This awareness led to

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

an interest in understanding elementary school teachers' perspectives on the implementation of blended learning. Gasson (2004) described transferability as the extent to which readers could generalize the study's findings within their own contexts and address the broader question of how applicable a theory might be beyond the specific research setting. Confirmability Referred to the degree of neutrality in the study's findings, ensuring that results were based solely on participants' responses rather than the researcher's biases or personal motivations. The researcher meticulously documented each step of the data analysis process using an audit trail to justify decisions made throughout the study. This careful record-keeping helped ensure that the findings genuinely represented participants' perspectives. Gasson (2004) acknowledged that complete objectivity in research was unattain-

able but emphasized the importance of minimizing bias to enhance credibility. Dependability Was achieved by ensuring that the study could be replicated by other researchers with consistent findings. If another researcher sought to reproduce the study, they should have access to sufficient details within the research report to achieve similar results. To establish dependability, an inquiry audit was conducted, allowing an external reviewer to assess the research process and data analysis for consistency and reliability. Additionally, a database was utilized to back up collected information and track any modifications in the research process. Gasson (2004) highlighted that dependability involved maintaining consistency across time, researchers, and analytical methods to ensure the study's validity and reliability.

3. Results and Discussion

In this chapter, the results of the study are presented and discussed with reference to the aim of the study. The themes that emerged from the data gathered are discussed in this chapter. The results present the description and background of the participants who are assigned to pseudonyms to conceal their identity.

3.1. Understanding of Teachers in Implementing Blended Learning Modality—Teachers' lived experiences in implementing the blended learning modality reveal both opportunities and challenges in navigating this instructional approach. Throughout the research, teachers expressed that blended learning allowed them to integrate technology into their teaching strategies, enhancing student engagement and flexibility in learning. However, they also encountered difficulties in balancing face-to-face and online instruction, as some students struggled with self-discipline and access to digital resources. Despite these challenges, teachers adapted by developing creative instructional

materials and fostering continuous communication with students and parents. Moreover, the research highlighted the emotional and professional adjustments teachers had to make in this transition. Many educators faced stress and burnout due to the increased workload of preparing both online and in-person lessons while ensuring student participation. They also emphasized the importance of professional development and peer collaboration in overcoming difficulties in technology integration. Despite these hurdles, teachers remained committed to fostering meaningful learning experiences, continuously refining their strategies to ensure that blended learning remained effective and inclusive.

3.1.1. Challenges in Technology Access—

Teachers encountered significant challenges in technology access while implementing blended learning, affecting learners' ability to participate effectively. Limited internet connectivity in many areas made it difficult for some learners to attend online classes and complete digital tasks on time. The lack of personal gadgets further restricted their engagement, as many had to share devices with family members or rely on borrowed equipment. Additionally, technical difficulties in navigating online platforms created frustrations, requiring teachers to provide constant support and alternative learning methods to ensure continued learning. Furthermore, the challenges of insufficient technological resources greatly impact teachers' ability to implement innovative strategies in blended learning. Limited access to digital tools and unreliable internet connectivity hinder their efforts to create engaging and effective learning experiences. Despite these obstacles, educators remain committed to adapting their teaching methods, finding creative ways to support learners with the resources available. These struggles highlight the importance of an educator's mindset, which is shaped by experiences and guided by core values that influence their actions and

3.1.2. Increased Teacher Workload—The implementation of blended learning has significantly increased teachers' workload, requiring more time and effort in lesson preparation. Designing instructional materials for both online and face-to-face settings demands careful planning to ensure that learners receive quality education regardless of the mode of delivery. Teachers must create interactive digital content while also preparing in-person activities, making lesson planning more time-consuming than traditional methods. This added responsibility often leads to longer working hours, as educators strive to meet the diverse needs of their learners. In addition to lesson preparation, teachers must balance online and face-to-

adaptability in the face of change (Kundu et al., 2021). Teachers' mindset and attitudes toward teaching are shaped by their experiences and core values, influencing how they adapt to challenges in blended learning. Limited technological resources, such as inadequate digital tools and unstable internet access, make it difficult to implement innovative teaching strategies effectively. Despite these obstacles, educators strive to find creative solutions to bridge these gaps, reinforcing the importance of their adaptability and commitment to educational change (Kundu et al., 2021). Learners face significant challenges in completing individual tasks in a blended learning environment, particularly due to distractions and low self-directedness. Limited internet access and a lack of personal gadgets further hinder their engagement, making it difficult to participate in online lessons and complete assignments on time. Additionally, technical difficulties with online platforms add to their frustrations, yet teachers continually adapt their strategies to maintain learner focus and motivation. These findings support the study on blended learning challenges, as highlighted by Gilmour (2020).

face tasks while managing an increasing number of paperwork and reports. Monitoring learner progress across multiple platforms requires continuous assessment and documentation, adding to administrative duties. The need to track online submissions, provide digital feedback, and comply with reporting requirements further contributes to their workload. Despite these challenges, teachers remain dedicated to delivering effective instruction, adapting their strategies to manage the demands of blended learning. Implementing blended learning requires educators to be highly skilled in teaching the same 21st-century competencies they expect learners to develop. Teachers must effectively communicate and collaborate with both colleagues

and learners while managing the complexities of integrating online and face-to-face instruction. The need for flexibility in adapting to new teaching-learning dynamics, supporting independent learning, and adjusting instructional strategies adds to their responsibilities. As a result, the increased workload from lesson preparation, balancing multiple tasks, and handling additional paperwork presents significant challenges for educators in this evolving learning environment (Rich, 2020). Educators work to evaluate learners' development efficiently while ensuring that teaching strategies foster both fairness and success in a blended learning setting. Instead of delivering the same instruction to all, they modify their approaches to address varying learner needs, demanding extra time for preparation and organization. This adjustment in teaching methods, combined with the challenge of managing numerous responsibilities, has greatly added to teachers' workload. These findings reinforce the study on the difficulties educators face in implementing blended learning, particularly in handling increased professional demands (Means et al., 2019). In addition, successful implementation of blended learning necessitates that educators acquire advanced in-

structional skills and specialized knowledge to effectively manage teaching responsibilities. These abilities are developed through ongoing training, hands-on experience, and continuous practice, enabling teachers to adjust to the challenges of both digital and in-person instruction. However, refining these skills increases their workload, as they must dedicate extra time to professional growth while navigating the intricate demands of blended learning (Barnett, 2019). Further, educators have a vital responsibility in helping learners develop the skills needed to interact, cooperate, and innovate using digital tools within a blended learning framework. These technology-centered competencies are crucial for academic achievement and preparedness for the evolving demands of the 21st-century world. However, designing interactive online and face-to-face instructional materials significantly increases teachers' responsibilities, making blended learning implementation both rigorous and time-intensive. This study reinforces research on blended learning, emphasizing the additional workload educators face in adapting to this instructional approach (Moran, 2020).

3.1.3. Student Engagement Setbacks — Utilizing blended learning presents several setbacks, particularly in maintaining student engagement. Many learners struggle with motivation, finding it challenging to stay focused without the constant supervision and structure of a traditional classroom. The flexibility of online learning can sometimes lead to procrastination, making it harder for teachers to ensure that students remain actively involved in their lessons. These engagement issues make it difficult to sustain a dynamic and interactive learning environment. Another significant challenge is the difficulty in monitoring student progress and providing timely feedback. With limited face-to-face interaction, teachers find it harder to as-

sess comprehension and address learning gaps effectively. The reduced opportunities for direct communication also limit meaningful engagement, making it challenging to foster collaboration and discussion among students. These struggles highlight the need for more structured support systems to enhance participation and accountability in blended learning. Teachers understand that learners progress at different rates and that true learning is better measured by mastery of skills rather than the time spent on tasks. Instead of rigidly following standardized schedules, they assess learners based on competency achievement and adjust their instruction to meet individual needs. However, setbacks in student engagement, such as a lack of motivation, make

it challenging for educators to ensure active participation and consistent progress. This statement supports the study on blended learning challenges, emphasizing the difficulties teachers face in keeping learners engaged and motivated throughout the learning process (Wang, 2019). In a blended learning environment, teachers acknowledge the varying abilities, special needs, and learning styles of each learner, ensuring that instruction is customized to foster individual development. They make efforts to modify their teaching strategies, addressing the distinct strengths and difficulties that learners encounter. However, setbacks in student engagement, such as low motivation and inconsistent participation, hinder the effectiveness of these personalized approaches. This perspective supports the study on blended learning implementation, highlighting the challenges educators face in maintaining active learner involvement (Nortvig et al., 2018). A key aspect of teachers' experiences in implementing blended learning is ensuring that learners still benefit from meaningful face-to-face interactions with their teachers and peers. Strengthening social connections and maintaining the human element in education remain essential, even as technology enhances flexibility in meeting diverse learning needs. However, teachers have observed setbacks in student engagement, as some learners struggle to stay con-

nected and actively participate in both online and in-person settings. These challenges highlight the need for strategies that balance technological advancements with interactive and engaging learning experiences (Diabat Aljalad, 2020). Furthermore, interventions that emphasize interactive and well-structured blended learning can enhance learners' confidence and engagement in their studies. In essence, effective instructional strategies that incorporate motivation can improve student participation and interest in blended learning. By integrating engaging and flexible approaches, educators can help learners adapt and succeed in this learning environment. Based on the figure above, three key themes emerged from the participants' responses: challenges in technology access, increased teacher workload, and learner engagement setbacks. Challenges in Technology Access theme suggests that teachers encounter difficulties in ensuring that all learners have access to the necessary digital tools and internet connectivity for blended learning. Limited availability of gadgets, unstable internet connections, and technical issues hinder smooth participation in online lessons. These barriers create disparities in learning experiences, making it difficult for educators to provide equal opportunities for all learners to engage effectively.

3.2. Strategies for the Problems Encountered In implementing Blended Learning —To address the challenges of blended learning, teachers maximize available resources by utilizing both digital and offline materials to ensure all learners can access lessons. They adapt instructional strategies by integrating low-tech solutions, such as printed modules and recorded lessons, for students with limited internet access. Creative use of existing technology, such as mobile devices and free educational platforms, helps bridge learning gaps. By being resourceful, teachers make learning more accessible and

adaptable to different student needs. Collaboration and continuous training also play a pivotal function in helping teachers navigate blended learning. Educators support one another by sharing best practices, lesson plans, and innovative teaching methods to ease the workload. Professional development workshops and training sessions help teachers improve their skills in using digital tools effectively. Additionally, involving parents and the community in the learning process fosters a supportive environment, ensuring students receive guidance both at home and in school.

Fig. 3. Emerging Themes on the Lived Experiences of Teachers in Implementing Blended Learning Modality

3.2.1. Maximizing Available Resources— To implement blended learning efficiently despite technological limitations, teachers make the most of available resources to support learners. Many rely on mobile data instead of Wi-Fi, allowing them to access online platforms and communicate with learners even in areas with limited connectivity. Teachers also encourage learners to use community learning hubs, such as local libraries or government centers, where they can access internet services and study materials. These strategies help bridge the digital divide, ensuring that learning continues despite internet challenges. Additionally, borrowing devices from schools has been a crucial coping mechanism for both teachers and learners who lack personal gadgets. Many schools lend tablets or laptops to learners, allowing them to participate in online lessons and complete digital activities. Teachers also guide learners in making the most of shared resources, such as using printed modules alongside borrowed devices to enhance their learning experience. By creatively utilizing available tools, educators ensure that blended learning remains ac-

cessible and effective for all learners. Statement 6 reflects that teachers actively collaborate with the barangay to provide learners access to community learning hubs, ensuring they have a space for studying despite limited resources. They also secure tablets from the school to assist those without personal devices, allowing more learners to participate in online activities. Furthermore, printing learning modules for those with no internet connection remains a vital strategy, ensuring every learner stays on track with their lessons despite technological setbacks. Designing effective blended learning activities focuses on customizing instruction, enhancing subject proficiency, and fostering essential 21st-century competencies. In overcoming implementation obstacles, educators make the most of existing resources by utilizing mobile data when Wi-Fi is scarce, ensuring continuous participation in virtual lessons. They also work alongside the community to set up learning hubs where learners can study and connect to online platforms. Furthermore, securing devices from schools helps close technological gaps, enabling more learners to engage in both digital and

in-person education, reinforcing the study on teachers' coping strategies through resource optimization (Bowen, 2019). Moreover, through proper guidance and demonstration, school leaders should encourage teachers and learners to use available tools responsibly, fostering a positive and progressive blended learning environment. This approach allows educators to maximize school resources, such as shared devices and community learning hubs, to ensure continuous and effective learning. A well-established blended learning culture provides opportunities for personalized and meaningful lessons, aligning instruction with each learner's optimal learning level. By utilizing available resources efficiently, teachers can enhance learning experiences despite challenges, reinforcing the study

on coping mechanisms in blended learning implementation (Alvarez, 2020). To effectively implement blended learning, teachers must fully grasp its instructional approach and address any misunderstandings about its strategies. As part of their coping mechanisms, they make the most of available resources, such as using mobile data when Wi-Fi is inaccessible to maintain seamless online learning. Collaborating with the community to provide access to learning hubs also enables learners to study in environments with better connectivity. Moreover, borrowing devices from schools plays a crucial role in narrowing the digital divide, ensuring that more learners can actively participate in both virtual and in-person learning experiences (Dziuban et al., 2018).

3.2.2. Teacher Collaboration and Training —Teacher collaboration and training play a crucial role in overcoming the challenges of blended learning implementation. Peer mentoring and resource sharing allow educators to support one another by exchanging best practices, lesson materials, and effective teaching strategies. Through collaborative efforts, teachers refine their instructional approaches, making blended learning more engaging and accessible for learners. By fostering a culture of teamwork, schools create a supportive environment where educators can continuously improve their skills and adapt to new teaching demands. Alongside teamwork, ongoing professional development through online training helps teachers enhance their digital competencies. Virtual workshops and courses provide educators with the necessary skills to navigate online platforms, create interactive lessons, and effectively manage digital classrooms. Support

groups dedicated to blended learning also offer teachers a space to share experiences, seek advice, and find encouragement from colleagues facing similar challenges. These collective efforts ensure that teachers are well-equipped to handle the demands of blended learning, leading to a more effective and sustainable implementation. To cope with the challenges of implementing the blended learning modality, teachers collaborate with their colleagues to clarify expectations, enhance time management strategies, and strengthen interpersonal communication skills. They also attend professional development training to better identify learning objectives, provide effective feedback, and foster positive relationships with both students and fellow educators. Through continuous collaboration and training, teachers refine their approaches to blended learning, ensuring a more effective and engaging learning experience for students (O'Doherty et al., 2018).

3.2.3. Parental and Community Involvement —Teachers effectively implement the

blended learning modality by actively involving parents and the community in the learning pro-

cess. They encourage parents to guide and support their children's studies at home, ensuring that students stay engaged and complete their tasks. By strengthening home-school partnerships, teachers create a collaborative learning environment that bridges classroom instruction with at-home learning. This connection helps reinforce lessons and provides learners with additional support beyond the school setting. Engaging the community is essential in overcoming the challenges of implementing blended learning. Teachers work with barangay officials to facilitate the smooth distribution of learning modules, ensuring that students have access to the necessary materials. By collaborating with local leaders, schools can reach more learners and provide them with the resources needed for academic success. These efforts demonstrate that effective blended learning requires a strong support system involving both families and the community. The participation of parents and the local community is vital for the successful implementation of the blended learning model. Ensuring an optimal class size is crucial, as smaller groups may restrict diverse student insights, while larger ones can limit the teacher's ability to provide adequate support. Through the involvement of families and the community, students gain extra assistance at home, making various subjects more adaptable to blended or digital learning settings. When guardians and community members take an active role in the educational journey, learners receive stronger encouragement, remain motivated, and are less likely to struggle with their academic development (Kareem, 2019). The strong support of parents and the community greatly contributes to the effective implementation of blended learning. Through active involvement, families and local stakeholders help ensure that learners stay on track by reinforcing the importance of meeting end-of-unit deadlines set by teachers. This shared responsibility enables students to recognize their past mistakes, establish new aca-

ademic goals, and develop stronger learning habits. With continuous guidance from both educators and the community, learners become more engaged and better prepared for future academic success (Barnett, 2019). Likewise, the study of (Davis et al., 2019) reinforces the idea that the successful implementation of blended learning relies on strong parental and community involvement. Teachers encounter challenges such as limited technological expertise, insufficient preparation time, and financial constraints, which can hinder effective instruction. However, the active participation of parents and, more importantly, the broader community helps alleviate these obstacles by offering essential support. Through collaborative efforts, schools gain access to necessary resources, and students receive guidance at home, ensuring that blended learning can be effectively put into practice despite these challenges. Based on the figure above, three key themes emerged from the participants' responses: maximizing available resources, teacher collaboration and training, and parental and community involvement. In implementing blended learning, this coping strategy emphasizes the use of diverse instructional methods to address the unique needs and learning preferences of learners. By integrating various digital tools, interactive activities, and flexible learning options, educators create a more engaging and inclusive learning experience. This approach acknowledges that learners have different interests, skills, and learning styles, ensuring that blended learning effectively supports their academic growth. Maximizing available resources, fostering teacher collaboration and training, and strengthening parental and community involvement are essential to the successful implementation of the blended learning modality. The effective use of technology, learning materials, and digital platforms ensures that students have access to quality education, regardless of their learning environment. Teacher collaboration and continuous professional devel-

Fig. 4. Emerging Themes on the Coping Mechanisms with the Challenges of Motivating Learners to Read

opment enhance instructional strategies, allowing educators to adapt to new teaching methods and address the diverse needs of learners. These

elements work together to create a structured and engaging learning experience that promotes student achievement.

3.3. Realization from Implementing Blended Learning—Implementing blended learning has provided valuable insights into how technology-enhanced education can support the developmental needs of learners. One key lesson learned is that a well-structured blended learning approach allows students to develop essential skills such as self-directed learning, critical thinking, and adaptability. By combining digital resources with traditional instruction, educators can create a more personalized learning experience that caters to different learning styles and paces. This approach ensures that students remain actively engaged while receiving the necessary sup-

port to strengthen their academic performance. Another important insight is that successful blended learning requires collaboration among teachers, parents, and the community to create an effective learning environment. Learners benefit significantly when they receive continuous guidance both at school and at home, reinforcing their academic progress and personal growth. Additionally, providing adequate training for teachers and maximizing available resources enable more efficient instructional delivery, further enhancing student learning outcomes. Through these lessons, blended learning proves to be an effective model for fostering both academic excellence and holistic development in learners.

3.3.1. Emphasizing flexibility in teaching—

Flexibility in teaching is essential for the effective implementation of the blended learning modality, as it allows educators to address the diverse needs of students. By incorporating both synchronous and asynchronous learning methods, teachers can provide real-time instruction while also allowing students to learn at their own pace. This balance ensures that learners receive immediate support when needed while having the flexibility to review materials independently. Such an approach accommodates different learning styles, making education more accessible and inclusive. Adapting teaching strategies to digital platforms is equally important in ensuring a seamless blended learning experience. Teachers must modify their instructional methods to effectively engage students in both online and face-to-face settings. Utilizing interactive tools, multimedia resources, and collaborative online activities helps maintain student interest and participation. With this adaptability, blended learning becomes a more dynamic and effective approach, fostering both academic growth and independent learning skills. Moreover, implementing a blended learning system requires redefining what makes an educator effective in this dynamic environment. Beyond traditional teaching skills, teachers must demonstrate flexibility by adapting their instructional methods, embracing innovative thinking, and developing professional habits that foster student engagement in both online and face-to-face settings. By valuing these less tangible qualities, educators can create a more responsive and inclusive learning experience, ensuring the success of blended learning for all students (Moran, 2020). Further, teachers' flexibility in adjusting their instructional methods is crucial for the effective implementation of individually structured blended learning. Since many students believe that

traditional classrooms provide a more familiar and effective learning environment where they can assess their engagement, effort, and participation, they often find individual tasks in blended learning challenging. By refining their teaching strategies, offering structured support, and guiding students through both online and in-person learning experiences, educators significantly enhance the success of blended learning programs (Wang, 2019). Furthermore, the study of Kareem (2019), accentuated that effectively managing and evaluating learners' progress in an individually structured blended learning model remains a significant challenge. However, research has demonstrated that teachers who exhibit flexibility in their instructional strategies—modifying assessments, delivering timely feedback, and providing personalized guidance—achieve greater success in addressing this issue. While learners may complete online activities, true comprehension and meaningful learning are attained only when teachers actively support and deepen their understanding, proving that adaptable teaching methods significantly enhance the effectiveness of blended learning. Kandakatla et al. (2020) highlighted in their study that teachers' flexibility in adapting instructional strategies is essential for the effective implementation of blended learning. Their findings revealed that educators who utilize group-task blended learning can enhance skill development, optimize educational resources, and improve overall learning quality by adjusting their approaches to meet diverse learner needs. This adaptability strengthens the education system's capacity, promotes inclusivity across different age groups, and ensures effective learning even in urgent training scenarios, demonstrating the crucial role of flexible teaching methods in blended learning success.

3.3.2. *Employing digital literacy—*

Employing digital literacy is essential for both teachers and learners, especially in the implementation of blended learning. Teachers must engage in continuous professional development to enhance their ability to integrate technology effectively into their teaching strategies. However, one of the key insights learned is the need for better ICT infrastructure to support seamless online and offline learning experiences. Without proper digital resources and training, both educators and learners may struggle to maximize the benefits of blended education. Osterlind (2019) emphasized that for learners to stay relevant in today's digital age, they must be motivated to develop digital competencies. The study also supports the idea that educators need to recognize the value of blended learning, particularly by integrating online discussions with traditional face-to-face teaching methods. Furthermore, it highlights that the successful implementation of blended learning relies heavily on teachers' digital literacy, particularly in using online monitoring systems to assess and track learners' progress effectively. Furthermore, Uz and Kundun (2018) found that a digital curriculum allows educators to plan and

implement differentiated instruction more efficiently by reducing the time spent creating content to meet diverse learners' needs. Their study highlights that the shift from traditional paper-based materials to multimedia resources—such as online books, videos, podcasts, and digital content from platforms like YouTube—requires teachers to possess strong digital literacy skills. This digital competence is crucial for the effective use of blended learning, enabling teachers to effectively integrate digital resources and create engaging learning experiences for their learners. Nevertheless, Barrett (2019) asserted that as the educational environment transforms, the resources utilized by educators and learners, both in and beyond the classroom, must evolve to address the shifting needs of learners. The blended learning approach embraces this transformation, providing a structure for the competencies and expertise required to succeed in a digital, interconnected world. The research indicates that for blended learning to be successful, educators must possess robust digital literacy skills to support learners in navigating these advancing educational tools and techniques.

3.3.3. Strengthening teacher and learner collaboration —Strengthening teacher and learner collaboration in blended learning required clear communication to ensure that learners understood expectations and learning objectives. Teachers had to find creative ways to motivate learners remotely, using interactive activities and digital tools to keep them engaged. At the same time, balancing discipline and encouragement became essential, as learners needed both structure and support to stay on track. By fostering an open and supportive learning environment, teachers were able to build stronger connections with learners despite the challenges of blended learning. Darling-Hammond et al. (2018) emphasize the

importance of promoting motivation and collaboration in a self-paced blended learning environment, where learners are guided to manage their time effectively within each unit of study rather than working without structure. However, the study also highlights that both teachers and learners face challenges with technical issues, such as unreliable online platforms, which disrupt the learning experience. Furthermore, limited internet access exacerbates engagement problems, making it difficult for learners to stay on track and for teachers to offer timely guidance and support, underscoring the need for strong teacher-learner collaboration to ensure effective blended learning implementation. Likewise, Davis et al. (2019) emphasize that the

individually tasked blended learning model naturally encourages collaboration, as learners can help one another or seek assistance from peers located in different areas through the online platform. While independent work on computers allows learners to progress through tasks, the study stresses that effective blended learning implementation relies on teachers facilitating collaboration among learners, enabling them to master content and skills together. This collaboration between teachers and learners is key to ensuring the success of blended learning. Statement 10 emphasized that the teacher stressed the importance of clear communication in keeping learners engaged and guided, especially in a blended learning environment. Despite the challenges of distance, they actively sought ways to sustain learner motivation while maintaining a balance between discipline and support. This highlights the teacher's commitment to fostering an effective and structured learning experience, even in a remote or hybrid setup. Also, statement 7 acknowledges that blended learning has shown that while technology is a valuable tool, a strong teacher-learner connection is essential for effective education. Teachers play a crucial role in initiating collaboration and fostering meaningful interactions with their learners. Maintaining awareness and prioritizing positive relationships ensures a supportive and engaging learning environment. Similarly, statement 8 highlighted that blended learning requires patience, resourcefulness, and a willingness to learn alongside learners. These qualities help educators adapt to challenges and effectively support students in a dynamic learning environment. Embracing continuous learning fosters growth for both teachers and learners, making education more meaningful and engaging. Finally, statement 2 accentuated that strong teacher-learner relationships are crucial, even in an online learning environment. To implement blended learning effectively, teachers must engage learners by capturing their interest. This

engagement fosters collaboration and strengthens connections within entire class. Based on the figure above, three themes emerged from the responses of the participants with regards to their insights and lessons learned from implementing blended learning which were: emphasizing flexibility in teaching, employing digital literacy, and strengthening teacher and learner collaboration. The implementation of blended learning has highlighted the importance of flexibility in teaching, allowing educators to adapt their instructional strategies to meet diverse student needs across various learning environments. It also underscores the necessity of employing digital literacy, as both teachers and students must develop technical skills to effectively navigate online platforms, access resources, and engage in meaningful learning experiences. Furthermore, the approach strengthens teacher and learner collaboration by fostering open communication, interactive discussions, and shared responsibilities in the learning process, promoting a more engaging and supportive educational experience. Ultimately, these themes emphasize the evolving role of educators in creating inclusive, technology-driven, and student-centered learning environments. The shift to blended learning has emphasized the need for flexibility in teaching, requiring educators to balance traditional classroom methods with digital instruction. Teachers have learned to adjust their lesson delivery, assessment strategies, and engagement techniques to accommodate diverse learning styles and varying student needs. This adaptability ensures that learning remains continuous and inclusive, even in the face of technological, logistical, or accessibility challenges. Likewise, blended learning has highlighted the crucial part of digital literacy, pushing teachers to develop proficiency in various online tools and platforms. Educators have recognized the importance of guiding students in navigating digital resources responsibly while ensuring meaningful and productive use of technology.

Fig. 5. Emerging Themes on the Educational Management Insights Drawn from the Findings of the Study

Beyond technical skills, digital literacy fosters critical thinking, problem-solving, and independent learning, preparing both teachers and students for an increasingly technology-driven educational landscape. The blended learning approach has reinforced the significance of teacher and learner collaboration, fostering a more interactive and engaging educational experience. Teachers have implemented strategies such as online discussions, collaborative projects, and real-time feedback to encourage active student participation. This strengthened communication and cooperation between educators and learners have led to increased motivation, deeper engage-

ment, and a more supportive learning environment. Generally, the implementation of blended learning has provided teachers with valuable insights, particularly in the areas of flexibility in teaching, digital literacy, and teacher-learner collaboration. Educators have learned to adapt their instructional strategies to accommodate diverse learning needs while effectively integrating technology to enhance student engagement and interaction. By fostering digital skills and strengthening collaboration, teachers have created a more inclusive, dynamic, and student-centered learning environment that supports continuous growth and innovation in education.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, I present a summary of the study, drawing on the findings to explore the implications and future directions. The goal of my research was to uncover the strategies used to motivate learners in a blended learning environment, the challenges faced by educators in maintaining student engagement, and the insights gained from the study’s findings.

4.1. Findings—To achieve the research objectives, I employed a qualitative phenomenological approach, utilizing thematic analysis. In line with Creswell (2020) guidelines, I used

open-ended interview questions to gain a genuine understanding of participants’ experiences. This method allowed participants to openly discuss their perspectives, providing an authentic

account of their experiences in implementing blended learning strategies. Through thematic analysis of the participants' responses, the following key findings and corresponding themes emerged: the Lived experiences of teachers in implementing blended learning modality included challenges in technology access, increased teacher workload, and learner engagement setbacks. The coping mechanisms for the problems encountered in implementing blended

learning modality identified were: maximizing available resources, teacher collaboration and training, and parental and community involvement. The insights and lessons gained from implementing blended learning in the study highlighted the importance of emphasizing teaching flexibility, enhancing digital literacy, and fostering stronger collaboration between teachers and learners.

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings related to the implementation of blended learning. In exploring the strategies employed by teachers in a blended learning environment, three key themes emerged from the responses of the participants: providing flexible learning options, integrating technology effectively, and fostering learner engagement. In providing flexible learning options, this theme suggests that teachers offer a variety of learning pathways and materials, allowing learners to choose the methods that best suit their individual learning styles and needs. This approach can include both synchronous and asynchronous activities, enabling learners to engage with content at their own pace and in a way that best supports their learning preferences. Integrating technology effectively involves utilizing digital tools and platforms to enhance learning experiences. Teachers are encouraged to use a range of digital resources, such as online courses, multimedia content, and interactive activities, to make learning more engaging and accessible. By incorporating technology in a meaningful way, teachers can enrich the learning process and provide learners with the skills needed to thrive in a digital world. Fostering learner engagement emphasizes the importance of creating interactive and motivating learning experiences in a blended learning environment. Teachers use various strategies, such as collaborative online activities,

real-time feedback, and gamification, to maintain learners' interest and participation. This engagement ensures that learners stay actively involved in the learning process, both online and offline, which is crucial for achieving learning outcomes in a blended learning model. These three themes suggest that teachers in a blended learning environment must employ a combination of strategies that cater to learners' diverse needs, fostering both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. By implementing these strategies effectively, educators can inspire learners to be proactive and self-directed, thereby ensuring a positive learning experience in a blended learning model. On the coping mechanisms with the challenges of implementing blended learning, three themes emerged from the responses of the participants: providing varied learning strategies, encouraging learner autonomy, and integrating blended learning across subjects. In providing varied learning strategies, this involves offering a diverse range of approaches to cater to the individual needs and preferences of learners. By utilizing different teaching methods, such as multimedia resources, online discussions, and interactive tools, educators can make learning more engaging and accessible to all learners. This approach recognizes that learners have varying interests, abilities, and learning styles, and seeks to accommodate these differences to create an inclusive learning environment. Encouraging learner self-reliance plays a

vital role in blended learning, especially when learners encounter challenges or setbacks in managing their own learning. Educators employ this coping mechanism by promoting self-directed learning, providing resources for independent study, and encouraging learners to take responsibility for their progress. By fostering a sense of ownership over their learning, educators help cultivate a growth mindset, motivating learners to persevere and succeed in a blended learning environment. Integrating blended learning across subjects is another coping mechanism used by educators to enhance engagement and relevance. By connecting blended learning to various subject areas or real-world contexts, teachers can make the learning experience more meaningful and applicable to learners. This interdisciplinary approach emphasizes the value of blended learning beyond the confines of a single subject, highlighting its importance in developing a well-rounded skill set for learners. These coping mechanisms underscore the importance of flexibility, learner autonomy, and integration in overcoming the challenges of blended learning. By providing diverse strategies, fostering independence, and emphasizing the inter-connectedness of learning, educators can empower learners to become confident and capable in a blended learning environment. On the educational management insights drawn from the findings of the study, the themes that emerged from the responses of the participants were fostering a positive learning culture, supporting differentiated learning activities, and recognizing the essential role of teachers in blended learning. Fostering a positive learning culture emphasizes the importance of creating an environment that supports blended

learning, where technology is celebrated and integrated effectively. Educational managers can facilitate this by creating spaces for online and in-person learning, organizing professional development opportunities on blended learning, and promoting the use of technology in the classroom. Supporting differentiated learning activities is crucial for addressing the diverse needs of learners in a blended learning environment. Educational managers can assist teachers by providing resources and training on how to design and deliver differentiated lessons that incorporate both digital and face-to-face learning. This includes offering varied levels of digital content, using adaptive technologies, and ensuring that instructional methods are tailored to learners' individual abilities and preferences. In recognizing the essential role of teachers in blended learning, it is critical to support educators with the tools, training, and resources they need to be successful in this model. Educational managers can provide teachers with professional development on digital literacy, access to high-quality digital tools, and opportunities for collaboration. By creating an environment that values and supports blended learning, educational managers empower teachers to be effective facilitators of learning in both virtual and physical spaces. Overall, these insights highlight the importance of leadership and management in fostering successful blended learning experiences. By prioritizing the development of a strong learning culture, supporting differentiated learning, and empowering teachers with the resources and training they need, educational managers can create an environment where all learners have the opportunity to succeed in a blended learning model.

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the findings of the study, it is important that the findings are properly relayed and used by the significant people whom this research was intended

for. Learners For learners, the future directions of blended learning implementation are vital in fostering self-motivation, enhancing digital literacy, and improving academic per-

formance. Tailoring blended learning experiences to individual preferences and interests can make learning more engaging and accessible. The shift towards blended learning not only prepares learners for lifelong learning but also equips them with the skills necessary for success in an increasingly digital world. Teachers The implementation of blended learning can help teachers create engaging and flexible learning environments that cater to diverse learner needs. By incorporating both online and face-to-face strategies, teachers can identify students' strengths and areas for improvement, providing differentiated instruction that maximizes learning outcomes. Teachers who effectively implement blended learning strategies can foster greater student engagement, improve retention, and cultivate critical thinking skills that prepare learners for the challenges of a digital world. Parents In blended learning environments, parents play an integral role in supporting their children's academic success by understanding how to navigate and utilize online learning platforms. Parents can create conducive learning spaces at home, establish routines for digital learning, and encourage active participation in both online and offline activities. When parents are engaged and informed about blended learning strategies, learners are more likely to remain motivated and productive, contributing to their overall academic growth and development. School Administrators Blended learning strategies may align with the educational goals of schools and can help them meet curriculum standards while enhancing student engagement and achievement. By investing in technology, resources, and professional development related to blended learning, school ad-

ministrators can ensure that teachers are well-equipped to facilitate dynamic learning environments that promote collaboration, critical thinking, and self-directed learning. Schools that prioritize blended learning often experience improved academic outcomes, with students benefiting from personalized learning experiences and flexible learning opportunities. Policy Makers Based on the findings of the study, policymakers can recognize the importance of effective blended learning implementation in fostering equitable access to quality education and enhancing learning outcomes across diverse communities. By supporting evidence-based blended learning strategies through policy initiatives, they can address educational disparities, boost digital literacy, and ensure that both teachers and learners have the necessary tools and resources. Investing in professional development programs for educators and supporting infrastructure for technology integration are essential elements of forward-thinking education policies aimed at improving learning experiences. Future Researchers Future researchers in the field of blended learning implementation can build upon the findings of this study to explore the effectiveness of various blended learning models across different educational contexts. By examining how teachers, learners, and educational systems adapt to blended learning environments, researchers can contribute to the development of best practices and evidence-based strategies that maximize the benefits of blended learning. Additionally, exploring the challenges faced by learners and educators in this modality can provide insights into improving the scalability and sustainability of blended learning approaches.

5. References

- Alvarez, A., Jr. (2020). Learning from the problems and challenges in blended learning: Basis for faculty development and program enhancement. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 15(2), 112–132. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4292631>

- Awaad, A. (2019). Students harness the skills of preparedness through blended learning [Retrieved from <https://www.blendedlearning.org/students-harness-the-skill-of-preparedness-through-blended-learning/>].
- Bandura, A. (1977). *Social learning theory*. Prentice-Hall.
- Barnett, R. (2019). The 3 biggest challenges of blended learning – and how to overcome them [Retrieved from <http://www.modernclassrooms.org/>].
- Bowen, R. S. (2019). *The handbook of blended learning environments: Global perspectives, local designs*. San Francisco.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2021). *Thematic analysis: A practical guide*. SAGE Publications.
- Bruner, J. (1973). *Going beyond the information given*. Norton.
- Creswell, J. W. (2020). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th). Sage.
- Darling-Hammond, L., Wilhoit, G., & Pittenger, L. (2018). Accountability for college and career readiness: Developing a new paradigm. *Education Policy Analysis Archives*, 22(86), 1. <https://doi.org/10.14507/epaa.v22n86>
- David, D. (2005). *Essentials of research design and methodology*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Davidson, R. J. (2000). Approach-withdrawal and cerebral asymmetry: Emotional expression and brain physiology. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 58.
- Davis, L. N., Gough, M., & Taylor, L. L. (2019). Online teaching: Advantages, obstacles and tools for getting it right. *Journal of Teaching in Travel & Tourism*, 19(3), 256–263.
- Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (Eds.). (2000). *Handbook of qualitative research* (2nd). Sage Publications.
- Diabat, M., & Aljallad, M. (2020). The effectiveness of employing blended learning on sixth-grade students' achievements and reflective thinking skills development in islamic education in the united arab emirates. *Multicultural Education*, 6(5), 216–223.
- Dziuban, C., Graham, C. R., Moskal, P. D., Norberg, A., & Sicilia, N. (2018). Blended learning: The new normal and emerging technologies. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 15(3), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-017-0087-5>
- Gasson, S. (2004). Rigor in grounded theory research: An interpretive perspective on generating theory from qualitative field studies. In *The handbook of information systems research*. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-59140-144-5.ch006>
- Gerodias, D. F. (2023). A focus on the contextualized learning activity sheets. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Educational Research and Innovation*, 1(1), 1–13.
- Gilmour, J. (2020). What are the challenges of implementing blended learning? [Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/maps/gcPg6FM4Wjx>].
- Glaser, B., & Strauss, A. (1967). *The discovery of grounded theory: Strategies for qualitative research*. Sociology Press.
- Gunn, T. M., & Hollingsworth, M. (2018). The implementation and assessment of a shared 21st-century learning vision: A district-based approach. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 45(3), 201–228.
- Gurley, L. E. (2018). Educators' preparation to teach, perceived teaching presence, and perceived teaching presence behaviors in blended and online learning environments [<https://eric.ed.gov/contentdelivery/servlet/ERICServlet?accno=EJ118139>]. *Online Learning*, 22(2), 197–220.

- Han, F., & Ellis, R. A. (2019). Identifying consistent patterns of quality learning discussions in blended learning. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 40, 12–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2018.09.002>
- Horn, M. B., & Staker, H. (2018). *Shaping culture for blended learning*. American Association of School Administrators.
- Kandakatla, R., Berger, E. J., Rhoads, J. F., & DeBoer, J. (2020). Student perspectives on the learning resources in an active, blended, and collaborative (abc) pedagogical environment. *International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy*, 10(2), 7–31.
- Kareem, A. A. (2019). The impact of blended learning on academic achievement and motivation to learn english in efl university students. *English Language Teaching*, 12(9), 97–106. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v12n9p97>
- Lee, J., Choi, H., & Kim, S. (2020). Perceived learning and satisfaction in online university courses: An update on determinants and structural relationships. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 21(4), 1–22.
- Li, K. C., Wong, B. T., & Tsang, K. W. (2020). A meta-analysis of the effectiveness of flipped classrooms in education. *Educational Research Review*, 30, 100314.
- Martin, F., Sun, T., & Westine, C. D. (2020). A systematic review of research on online teaching and learning from 2009 to 2018. *Computers & Education*, 159, 104009. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2020.104009>
- McGee, P., & Reis, A. (2021). Effective teaching online: A literature review. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 13(2), ep293.
- of Education (MOE), M. (2020). Developing a culture of blended learning: Key strategies and lessons. *Philippine Education Quarterly*, 5(2), 25–32.
- Patton, M. Q. (2002). *Qualitative research and evaluation methods* (3rd). Sage Publications.
- Rahman, M. M. (2021). An analysis of blended learning in higher education. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 10(1), 123–130.
- Rajab, A., Bashir, A., Elsayed, W., Hamouda, M., Al-Sharif, M., & Aldawood, A. (2020). Blended learning during covid-19 pandemic: Advantages, challenges and future perspectives. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 34(6), 115–126.
- Romiszowski, A. (2020). Online learning: Meeting new challenges. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 68(1), 1–12.
- Samy, M., Mohamed, M., & El-Sayed, K. (2020). Blended learning and student engagement: An empirical study. *Education and Information Technologies*, 25(6), 5381–5395.
- Staker, H., & Horn, M. B. (2017). Designing a blended learning system: Key elements and implementation strategies. *Journal of Blended Learning Research*, 3(1), 45–60.
- Tan, C., & Hew, K. F. (2020). The impact of flipped classroom on learning: A meta-analysis. *Educational Technology & Society*, 23(3), 1–12.
- Wang, Y., Zhang, D., & Wang, J. (2020). Teacher presence and student engagement in blended learning environments. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 51(3), 813–826.